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BIOINSPIRED GRAPHENE/LIQUID CRYSTALLINE POLYMER NANOCOMPOSITE COATINGS FOR TRIBOLOGICAL APPLICATIONS

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Outline

- Background
- Bioinspired GNP/LCP coatings
 - Multiscale design and rational assembly strategy
 - Layered composites
 - Tribological properties
- Conclusions

Background: Polymer coatings for tribological applications

- Friction between mechanical components
 - Large energy waste
 - High wear, reduced reliability
- Polymer composite coatings
 - Avoid direct contact between metals
 - Reduce friction

Wear Loading: Sliding Requirement: Low Friction, Low Wear

Wear Loading: Fretting, Sliding Requirement: Minimize Friction & Wear

Background:

Design principles for wear-resistant polymer composites

Background: Multilayer graphene – an emerging solid lubricant

Spear *et al.*, *Nano Today*, 2015, 10, 301–314

Berman *et al.*, *Adv Func Mater*, 2014, 24, 6640-6646.

Conventional solid lubricants

- **Layered structure:** graphite, MoS₂, h-BN
- Weak interlayer vdW forces: low friction

Multilayer graphene

- **interlayer shear** to reduce friction
- High mechanical strength: to **suppress wear**
- Impermeable to water and gas: to inhibit **corrosion induced wear**

Multiscale design and rational assembly

Liquid crystalline polymers (LCP)

- Low viscosity
- Good adhesion with metal substrate

Graphite nanoplatelets (GNP)

- Multilayer for low friction
- Pi-pi interaction with LCP

Goals:

- Increasing level of **robustness** and **alignment**
- Higher **wear resistance** and lower **friction**

Tribological properties of LCP: Effect of LC phase

Tribological properties of GNP/LCP coatings: Wear

Morphologies

Tribological properties of GNP/LCP coatings: Friction

- Increasing CoF with increasing GNP content: due to the **rough wear tracks** resulted from the GNP with edges sticking out after plowing
- Unstable CoF of LCP and 0.2wt% GNP: non continuous, **patches of transfer films**
- Shorter run in period for 10 wt % GNP:
 - almost **no plowing**, suggesting a low wear rate
 - Due to **better alignment**

Tribological properties of GNP/LCP coatings

GNP content	0.2 wt %	2 wt %	10 wt %
Increase in CoF*	6 %	40 %	53 %
Decrease in W_s^*	38 %	45 %	83 %

* Compare to values of pure LCP

Mechanical properties of the coating

Increasing stiffness and hardness, **higher wear resistance**

Morphologies of worn surfaces of coatings

LCP:

- Deep scuffs
- Soft but smooth surface

Increasing GNP:

- Harder but rougher surface
- **Higher CoF**

Isolated GNP

Overlapped GNP

Morphology of transfer film on counterpart ring

High GNP content:

- GNP transferred from coating to steel counterpart
- Continuous, thin transfer film
- **higher wear resistance**

Heterogeneous structure: GNP/LCP bilayer

Heterogeneous structure in biological systems

Tooth

Stuart AR, Adv. Funct. Mater. 2013, 23, 4423–4436

- **Hard** outer layer (Enamel): wear resistance
- **Soft** inner layer (Dentin): maintain integrity

Skin

Qi et al., ACS Nano 2018, 1062-1073

Homogeneous

Heterogeneous

- Outer layer (highly aligned GNP): **wear resistance**
- Inner layer (LCP): **maintain integrity/good adhesion** with substrate

Tribological properties of GNP/LCP bilayer structure

Comparison of transfer films

- More **uniform transfer film** for bilayer structure due to the higher GNP concentration on the surface

Long-term performance

- Further reduction in CoF for bilayer structure
- Continuous reduction in wear rate for both homogeneous and bilayer structure up to 10.8 km (6 h)
- Increase in wear rate of bilayer structure for sliding distance of 18 km (10 h)

Morphologies of worn surfaces

- **Smother surface** with increasing sliding distance: lower friction
- Almost **worn out GNP layer** after 18 km: higher wear rate

Summary

Orders of magnitude reduction in wear rate

- Increasing hardness
- Thin and uniform transfer films

Reduction in friction and wear by bilayer structure

- Highly aligned surface layer
- Uniform transfer film

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